

D 1.5 – Open Call Summary Report 2

Open Call 2 – January 2024

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Author(s) and Institution(s)	Neal Reeves – King's College London Gefion Thuermer – King's College London
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1 Executive Summary

IMPETUS is a Horizon Europe project which supports and enables citizen science initiatives. As part of these activities, IMPETUS provides funding and training through a citizen science accelerator for which initiatives are recruited through an open call. In this deliverable, we summarise the second IMPETUS open call which ran from the 10th of January to the 15th of March 2024 ahead of the start of the IMPETUS accelerator in June 2024.

The main findings are as follows:

- A total of 225 applications were received from 36 countries including 22 European Union member states, 8 associated countries and 6 third countries.
- The most common country from which applications were received was Italy with 38 applications followed by Spain with 30 applications
- A total of 32 applications were deemed ineligible for review while 192 proceeded to the evaluation process. 98 projects were rejected at this time and a total of 94 were invited to interview. Ultimately, 48 projects were successful while 46 of the interviewed projects were not.
- Significantly more new projects applied than established projects with 174 applications from kickstarting projects and 51 applications from sustaining projects.
- Applications were evenly distributed between the two main challenges with 86 applications for Challenge 1 – *Sustainable Lifestyles* and 82 applications for Challenge 2 – *Justice and Equity*. A smaller – but substantial – number of applications was received for Challenge 3 – Citizen Science for and with Communities.

2 Introduction

IMPETUS is a Horizon Europe project which supports and enables citizen science initiatives. As part of these activities, IMPETUS provides funding and training through a citizen science accelerator for which initiatives are recruited through an open call. IMPETUS aims to provide training through the accelerator to a total of 125 citizen science initiatives (CSIs) over three years. In the first year of the open call, 34 projects participated in the accelerator (29 kickstarting, 4 sustaining) and the aim with this second call was to recruit another 46 projects (35 kickstarting, 11 sustaining).

The IMPETUS open call is open to applicants from across the European Union, overseas countries and territories linked to EU member states and associated countries including countries negotiating an association agreement with Horizon Europe. Applicants are offered two types of grants: kickstarting grants supporting the setup of new projects with funding of €20,000 and sustaining grants supporting further development and/or sustainability of existing projects with funding of €10,000. Regardless of funding and grant type, projects are invited to apply to the same call through the same application process and successful projects join the same accelerator where they receive funding, supporting, training and mentoring over a seven-month period (increased from six months during the first call).

This report covers the development and implementation of the second open call which took place between the 10th of January and the 15th of March 2024. We detail the different stages of the call (preparation, implementation, eligibility check and evaluation) as experienced by various stakeholders including applicants, consortium members, external experts and the IMPETUS citizen panel. We provide key statistics on the outcomes of the applications including numbers of eligible, interviewed and successful applications, countries of origin of the applications and applicants, inclusiveness and equity details and the focus of each proposal.

Additionally, we describe the relationship with applicants particularly in terms of email correspondence through our dedicated call email, 1:1 advisory sessions, as well as a series of webinars conducted to inform applicants of the call and answer any queries. Finally, we identify lessons learned and summarise improvements to be implemented in the third and final call in 2024. Relevant documentation for this open call as referred to in this document (guide for applicants, FAQ, proposal templates and declaration of honour) were submitted as part of D 1.2 in December 2023 and were made available to all applicants through the IMPETUS website.

3 Summary of Call Process

The IMPETUS open call is a recurring funding call intended to support European citizen science initiatives. The project has a particular focus on those initiatives addressing and providing data to measure indicators associated with the UN Sustainable Development Goals and for this year (and this year only) an additional challenge was added to the call to support grassroots, 'bottom-up' citizen science activities. Each year of the open call follows the same structure made up of five key phases: preparation, call, eligibility checks, reviews and interviews. A summary of the phases can be seen in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Overview of second call timeline as communicated to applicants

The open call process concludes at the end of the final selection stage and at this point, the successful candidates are passed onto consortium partners to proceed with onboarding. Zabala is responsible for due diligence and contracts while Science for Change is responsible for the accelerator including workplans and budgets. A detailed timeline of the relevant phases and key dates for the second call is provided in table 1 below.

Date	Milestone	Description
December 2023	Preparations Complete	All documents prepared, uploaded to IMPETUS website and EasyChair instance updated.
10 th January 2024	Call Opens	Open call open for applications. EasyChair instance opens. Website and

		social media channels updated to announce opening.
24 th January 2024	First Webinar	Three hour webinar with potential applicants giving information and offering opportunities for questions
28 th February 2024	Second Webinar	Three hour webinar with potential applicants giving information and offering opportunities for questions
15 TH & 18 th March 2024	Reviewer Webinar	Webinar with external reviewers introducing challenges and detailing review process.
15 th March 2024 ¹	Call Closes	EasyChair instance closes to applications. Eligibility check commences.
18 th March 2024	Eligibility Checks Complete	
19 th March 2024	Reviewing Commences	Applications assigned to reviewers.
11 th April 2024	Reviewing Closes	Deadline for submission of reviews.
15 th -26 th April 2024	Interviews	Interview process begins.
29 th April 2024	Final Selection	Consortium selects projects.
29 th April 2024	Notifications Sent	

Table 1: timeline of key dates

This deliverable will detail the individual stages of the second open call in further detail. IMPETUS features two open calls – the accelerator open call and an open call for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. This deliverable covers only the accelerator open call and any reference to ‘open call’ is a reference to the accelerator call only.

¹ While the call was scheduled to close on the 14th of March, the decision was made to extend the call until midday on the 15th of March to facilitate any final submissions

3.1 Preparation

For this year's open call, the IMPETUS consortium reaffirmed the definition for citizen science agreed on by the consortium for the first open call. The open call consisted of two main challenges: one from the IMPETUS consortium as defined in the grant agreement around Sustainable Lifestyles and a second defined by the IMPETUS citizen panel. In addition, in response to limited applications for such projects in the first call, the consortium chose to implement a third challenge *Citizen Science with and for Communities* intended to target and support bottom-up, citizen-led initiatives.

The consortium challenge was defined in part in the grant agreement. However, some changes were made to the planned topics and subchallenges. In addition to the planned SDGs 2 (Zero Hunger) and 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) was moved from the 3rd to the 2nd call. This resulted in three subchallenges: Food, Mobility and Waste. In addition, cross-cutting SDGs for all three challenges were largely the same as the first challenge and included SDGs 4 (Quality Education), 5 (Gender Equality) and 10 (Reduced Inequalities). SDGs 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and 13 (Climate Action) were in part represented through the mobility subchallenge but will be given more of a focus in the third open call.

In order to create the Citizen panel challenge, IMPETUS drew on the panel of citizen science practitioners with an additional 13 practitioners recruited to the call². These practitioners were recruited through a call published on the IMPETUS website, and a simple application form asking candidates to describe their relationship to citizen science, and outlining diversity criteria. Out of this, the thirteen most suitable candidates were selected by KCL and AE such that the panel would play a role in both the Accelerator and the Prize call.

The panel met once in October and twice in November 2023, through a combination of Microsoft Teams calls and asynchronous collaboration on documents in a shared folder on Google Drive. The first meeting was focused on introductions and an initial brainstorm and took place on the 13th of September. Following this, an interim meeting was held on the 13th of November to discuss progress and narrow ideas down. A final meeting was held on the 29th of November to reach a consensus and decide on a challenge. The challenge text was then finalised by the IMPETUS consortium, to ensure the language was aligned with other call documents, and approved by the panel under the title *Justice and Equity* (see D1.2).

Alongside the creation of the challenges, KCL created three key documents: the Guide for Applicants, an FAQ, and an application form (see all in D1.3). These were

² In addition to 10 new practitioners, 3 previous practitioners opted to leave the panel and so were replaced.

largely based on the first call but were refined in response to queries and issues from the first call (see D1.4) and to reflect the change in focus for the second call.

Lastly, KCL prepared the application submission platform EasyChair. This included questions applicants needed to answer about their proposed project, the type of grant and challenge they applied for, the type of applicant (e.g. individual, consortium) as well as an initial impact assessment. Questions for the latter were aligned with WP5 to allow for later use in the projects' impact assessment. On the whole, the EasyChair configuration was similar to that used in last year's call, with updates to fit the new challenges and some change in question text. A user guide was provided to assist applicants with making their application through EasyChair.

3.2 Implementation

The second open call launched on 10th of January alongside the open call for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. This decision was made to closely align the two calls and leverage synergies between the two processes and follows the decision to similarly align the two calls during the first open call conducted in 2023. The accelerator call was hosted on the IMPETUS website alongside a separate page covering the European Union Prize for Citizen Science, with each page featuring a short description and link to the other call for participants who may wish to apply to both or for whom one call may not be appropriate. It should be noted, however, that the accelerator call accepted applications for a slightly longer period than the prize call to allow applicants to apply to both if they wished without having to aim for deadlines on the same day.

3.2.1 Call Information

The main source of information for potential applicants was the IMPETUS website with a dedicated page on the open call as with the first call which can be found at <https://impetus4cs.eu/opencall/>. The website served as the entry point for the call with all of the documentation and information that an applicant would need to be able to apply, links to webinars, contact details and links to register for 1:1 calls with the IMPETUS team. Applicants who wished to apply were linked to EasyChair to submit and manage their application.

Prior to making their application, prospective applicants were encouraged and advised to read documentation available on the IMPETUS website, particularly the Guide for Applicants and FAQ documents. These documents were prepared prior to the launch of the call and built on documents, questions and requests from the first open call. The Guide for Applicants in particular contained key information required to submit an application including the call purpose and aims, the challenges and subtracks, eligibility requirements, key dates and the evaluation process. In addition, the website featured template documents for applicants to use. Where these were insufficient, the website also linked to other resources to ask for further information (see "Applicant Support" below).

The application process was broadly unchanged from the first call. Applicants were asked to complete a short proposal with a maximum length of 4 pages by filling in an application form available from the IMPETUS website. Although the exact wording of the questions was different than in the first open call, the focus of the questions was similar with questions divided once again into four sections: *Idea, Implementation, Team and Community* and *Impact*. Alongside this, applicants were required to provide some administrative details through EasyChair and to upload a signed, dated declaration of honour. Applicants to challenge 3 (Citizen Science for and with Communities) were asked to submit a letter of support from their community with a maximum length of 2 pages. A template was provided to support them with this.

While the application forms were changed for the second call, some applicants instead submitted the unchanged forms from the first open call. We believe this was due to two factors: firstly, some applicants aimed to re-use their applications from the first call with minor updates. Secondly, however, due to a bug in the IMPETUS website, it was possible under very specific circumstances to download the call documentation from the first call rather than the second call. This is unlikely to have impacted a significant number of applicants as the triggering the bug was quite difficult and required very specific actions. Moreover, the documentation would clearly be out of date (e.g., stating 2023 and referring to last year's challenges). This bug was also fixed at a very early stage.

Nevertheless, due to the possibility – however unlikely – that applicants may have inadvertently submitted the wrong documents due to circumstances beyond their own control, it was decided that both the first call and second call application forms would be accepted. Reviewers were offered specific guidelines about which questions to consider when evaluating applications as while the wording of the questions was extremely similar, the order of the questions sometimes differed. Evaluations were checked to ensure that applicants using one particular set of forms did not receive significantly lower or higher scores and no such effect was observed, likely due to the similarity between the forms and in terms of the questions asked.

3.2.2 Applicant Support

In addition to the helpline and following the approach used for the first open call, we ran two webinars to provide information for potential applicants and to field any questions. Webinars took place over Microsoft Teams and were advertised (with attendance registered through) EventBrite and Skiddle as well as being disseminated through IMPETUS social media channels. Each webinar was also recorded and published to YouTube and the IMPETUS website. The first webinar took place on the 24th of January and the second took place a month later on the 28th of February. Each webinar lasted for an hour and a half with information provided on the application and evaluation processes for both the accelerator and prize open calls. At the end of each webinar, a Q&A session was held to allow prospective applicants to ask any questions they might have.

Webinar	Registrations	Attendees	Views (7/10/24)
Open Call Webinar 1	74	55	278
Open Call Webinar 2	130	94	112
Total	204	149	390

Table 2: Webinar registration, attendance and view counts

In addition, a dedicated email inbox was available to participants. A total of 166 email queries were received and answered during the call process. The most common query topics were as follows:

1. Eligibility questions by country
2. Suitability of projects for kickstarting/sustaining grants
3. Suitability of projects for the different challenges
4. Eligibility of particular costs for the call
5. Eligibility of legal entities/consortium members
6. Whether it was possible to submit two applications (either due to distinct organisations submitting or a second application for previously successful applicants)
7. Questions around the eligibility of equipment costs
8. Questions regarding whether it was possible to resize the application form

Registration, attendance and YouTube view counts can be seen in table 2 below. Both webinars were very similar and used the same presentation materials although the questions asked by applicants naturally varied between the two webinars. While registration for both webinars was made available as soon as the call launched, there was a short delay between each webinar and it being uploaded to YouTube and dissemination activities were broadly focused on the first webinar initially, moving to the second webinar after the first webinar was completed.

In addition, for this year's call, 1:1 sessions were introduced. These allowed applicants to sign up for 10 minute calls with a member of the KCL IMPETUS team to discuss any questions they had about the application process. This call would take place over Microsoft Teams and applicants would apply through the Calendly service with an opportunity to submit their questions in advance. The intention of these sessions was to allow less experienced applicants to seek further clarification than may otherwise be offered to encourage them to submit their project ideas and seek funding and support. In practice, however, it was difficult to identify whether this target community were truly making use of the 1:1 sessions.

The effort required to run 1:1 sessions was very high. Prior to each call, a member of the team would need to review the calendly information and calls were regularly scheduled with very little notice. No-shows were high and even among the applicants who attended the sessions, few ultimately submitted an application to the call. Moreover, questions regularly strayed beyond the subjects intended to be addressed for the 1:1s – in fact, most applicants seemed to be seeking feedback and guidance with their project idea, which was something the team could not offer. Ultimately, for the time investment offered, it was felt that the 1:1 sessions offered limited benefit.

3.3 Eligibility Checks

Upon the closure of the application process, KCL conducted eligibility checks for all received applications. Eligibility criteria were identical for challenge 1 and 2, but were slightly different for challenge 3 – see table 3 below. All eligibility criteria were listed in the Guide for Applicants and discussed in the call webinars.

	All challenges	Challenge 3 only
Kickstarting and Sustaining	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organisation and project located in European Research Area or other country listed in Guide for Applicants 2. Declaration of Honour (signed) 3. Application form maximum of 4 pages with no changes to form 4. Proposal to implement citizen science activities (aligned with IMPETUS definition) 5. Relevant to and aligned with IMPETUS challenges/subtracks 6. Only one application per legal entity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Letter of support (maximum 2 pages) showing prior engagement with the community
Kickstarting only	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Project status (not started or started but not implemented) 	
Sustaining only	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Project status (actively engaging with a citizen) 	

	science community collecting/analysing data or completing other project tasks)	
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Table 3: Required eligibility criteria based on challenge

As well as these criteria, projects which clearly could not be successfully carried out during the IMPETUS accelerator as they required more than the 7 available months or budgeted for over €20,000 (for kickstarting projects) or €10,000 (for sustaining projects) were deemed ineligible. A total of 32 projects were removed as ineligible while 193 projects were sent for review.

3.4 Reviews

Each eligible project was reviewed by a panel of IMPETUS consortium members and external experts. A total of 571 reviews were conducted by 9 internal and 14 external reviewers between the 19th of March and the 11th of April. Reviewers were selected from a pool of experts associated with IMPETUS and its consortium partners, reviewers who participated in the first open call review process and experts in the challenges and subtracks of the call recruited through recommendations from existing experts. Additionally, members of the citizen panel with relevant expertise were also invited to review if – and only if – they had not made an application to the call.

Each application was assigned to two external reviewers and one internal IMPETUS reviewer. Wherever possible, reviewers were assigned to cover three distinct types of expertise:

1. Topical expertise – expertise in either the challenge theme or subtrack provided by an external reviewer
2. Citizen Science expertise – expertise in citizen science more broadly provided by an external reviewer
3. IMPETUS expertise – expertise in the IMPETUS project and the goals of the open call provided by members of the IMPETUS consortium

Reviewers were assigned to projects typically based on the challenge or subtrack which the application focused on. However, reviewers were asked for their expertise and areas of interest and where appropriate, projects were assigned to specific reviewers based on the project description.

One exception to this process was the third challenge (Citizen science For and With Communities). Applicants to this particular challenge could cover any topic and it was therefore impractical to recruit reviewers to cover the full scope of these topics, particularly at short notice for projects submitted late in the application period. In addition, a key focus of this challenge was to recruit bottom-up, community-led citizen science projects. While projects were asked to provide a letter of support evidencing engagement with the community, it was usually not possible to

ascertain from the letter alone whether the project was truly an example of a bottom-up project or not.

Therefore, applicants to challenge 3 similarly received 3 reviews including 1 internal and 2 external reviewers, but this challenge used a specific panel of experts with experience conducting and researching bottom-up projects. Reviewers were assigned as follows:

1. Bottom-up citizen science expertise provided by an external reviewer
2. Bottom-up citizen science expertise provided by an external reviewer
3. IMPETUS expertise provided by a member of the IMPETUS consortium

Reviewers for this particular challenge were asked to consider whether projects were truly examples of bottom-up citizen science and whether they would be feasible for the community to manage and conduct in addition to the review criteria common to all three challenges.

When reviewing, reviewers were asked to complete a review form within EasyChair by assigning a comment and score across four areas: idea, implementation, team and community, and impact (aligning with the four sections of the application form). Scores consisted of a number from 1 to 5 where 1 was very poor and 5 was excellent. To assist reviewers with the review process, each reviewer was provided with a scoring grid indicating how to distinguish between each score for each answer.

3.5 Interviews

IMPETUS conducted a total of 96 interviews over nine days, between 15th – 26th April 2024. As with the first call, shortlisted applicants received an invitation to interview by email, outlining the process:

The interview will consist of a short presentation by you of your proposed project, followed by questions from a panel. The presentation can be up to five minutes long, and should cover your idea, implementation plan, team, and anticipated impact. You may bring slides, but you do not have to. The Q&A will be 15 minutes, with a panel of two members of the IMPETUS team.

Interviewers were members of the IMPETUS consortium, specifically from KCL (chairing on all interviews), Nesta, T6, and Science for Change. All interviewers were provided with the application form and reviews for the specific project. Additionally, interviewers were given a set of example questions that could be used during the interview process if necessary, along with some specific questions derived from the review process. Interviewers recorded their notes and thoughts about each project, and their personal preference for them to proceed into the Accelerator (Yes/Maybe/No) in an excel table. Based on this information, the IMPETUS consortium made a final decision about projects to join the accelerator in a call on 29th April. Applicants were informed of the outcome on the same date. At this point, successful applicants were passed on to partners SfC and Zabala, to proceed with contract negotiation and onboarding into the accelerator.

4 Call results

In this section, we will outline the outcomes and statistics of the open call process.

4.1 Eligibility

During the eligibility checks, applications were checked for adherence to the criteria of the call as described in the guide for applicants.

A total of 32 projects (14%) were deemed to be ineligible at this stage, which was in line with the first round of the call with an 11% ineligibility rate. We believe this low rate is due to the role that EasyChair plays in preventing some errors (such as overlength applications) from occurring. However, it should be noted that a further 24 applications had budget issues including missing overheads which may have exceeded the budget provided and may therefore not have been possible to conduct within the accelerator using the resources provided. To avoid unfairly penalising less experienced applicants, these applications were reviewed in spite of these issues.

The reasons for applications being deemed ineligible in the second IMPETUS open call can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** below. Many of these applications had multiple issues and have only been described under the main issue impacting the application.

Issue	Count (Percentage)
Not Citizen Science	11
Not bottom-up (Challenge 3)	6
Budget exceeds €20,000	5
Not relevant to challenge	3
Changes made to application form	2
Declaration of honour missing	2
Not based in eligible country	2
Duplicate submission	1

Table 4: Ineligible applications by main criterion

The most common reason for projects being rejected was that they did not meet the Impetus definition of Citizen Science, typically as they focused on the design and/or development of a product rather than a research project and/or involved little to no citizen engagement. Six projects were deemed ineligible as they were submitted to challenge 3 but clearly included no bottom-up element(s). Projects where the budget clearly exceeded the maximum amount were also rejected. Two projects were received from South America and Uganda respectively and the proposed activities would have been outside of the European Research Area.

4.2 Reviews

A total of 193 eligible applications proceeded to review. All applications received three reviews from the review team including 2 external reviewers from a pool of 14 reviewers and 1 internal reviewer from within the IMPETUS consortium. Every IMPETUS partner contributed to the review process except for Ars Electronica (who were running the review process for prize applications in parallel) and EUSEA (who had limited time available to contribute to reviews).

The review process was similar to that for the first call. Each reviewer assigned up to five points for each of four application areas (with a maximum of 20 points). However, applicants needed to score at least an average of 3 in each area across all 3 reviewers to be considered for interview and ultimately only the top 96 applicants were selected for interview. This differed from last year where applicants needed to reach a minimum average of 12 points for interview.

4.2.1 Average scores

Applicants needed to reach a minimum of 12 points on average, and must not have been scored below 3 in any one area by any one reviewer, to qualify for an interview. On average, projects achieved an overall score of 14.08 for Challenge 1 (Sustainable Lifestyles), 14.70 for challenge 2 (Justice and Equity) and a lower 13.01 for challenge 3 (Citizen Science with and for Communities). This necessitated that a higher threshold was used and to be considered for interview, projects ultimately needed an average score of 15 with at least 3 in each area.

	Kickstarting	Sustaining	Overall
Sustainable Lifestyles	13.95	14.42	14.08
Justice and Equity	14.48	15.60	14.70
Citizen Science with and for Communities	13.54	11.51	13.01

Table 5: Average review score by challenge and track

Scores were generally similar across the three challenges with challenge 3 applications scoring lower overall than challenge 1 and 2 applications. This aligns with the limited bottom-up citizen-led activities seen in challenge 3 projects. Sustaining projects scored more highly than kickstarting projects for the first two challenges, but this trend was reversed in the bottom-up challenge 3 projects. This is because the more established projects typically were not citizen-led and had lower scope for citizen engagement than the newly proposed projects.

4.4 Reviewer Evaluation Comparison

A total of 24 reviewers participated in the evaluation process for the second open call with 10 reviewers drawn from the IMPETUS consortium ('internal' reviewers) and 14 external experts invited to participate ('external' reviewers). Each application received three reviews typically from 1 internal reviewer and 2 external reviewers with the first external reviewer assigned on the basis of expertise relevant to the challenge and the second external reviewer assigned on the basis of expertise in citizen science more broadly. As a result, there was significant potential for disagreement between the reviewers and this diversity of opinions was an intentional feature of the review process. Broadly speaking, final evaluation of projects would be based on the average of these three reviews with further consideration of the comments and justifications behind these scores should any significant disagreements arise.

We took a number of steps to manage potential disagreements between reviewers and to encourage consistency in results. Firstly, the resources shared with reviewers were intended to limit ambiguity in the review process. During an initial training session, reviewers were also able to ask questions and given examples from previous calls to help clarify scores. Moreover, it should be noted that wherever possible, reviewers were assigned to a particular challenge only. For example, 4 individuals with significant experience in bottom-up citizen science projects were assigned to challenge 2 and (with one exception) these reviewers only reviewed projects from that challenge.

Nevertheless, we performed an evaluation of the average scores given by each reviewer to try to understand the extent of any disagreement and the potential impact this may have had on applicants' total scores. These scores are presented in table 6 below. To protect the anonymity of reviewers, pseudonyms have been used instead.

Reviewer	Internal/External	Average Score
A	Internal	13.6
B	External	14.3

C	Internal	14.1
D	External	15.7
E	Internal	13.32
F	External	17.1
G	External	12.0
H	External	16.5
I	Internal	13.9
J	External	14.7
K	External	11.7
L	External	15.12
M	External	13.6
N	External	15
O	Internal	12.3
P	External	16.8
Q	External	14.2
R	Internal	11.8
S	External	13.6
T	Internal	12.2
U	Internal	14.4
V	Internal	15.3
W	External	13.9

Table 6 – Overall Average Scores by Reviewer

The overall average across all reviewers was 14.1 with a standard deviation between reviewers of 3.56. All reviewers were within one standard deviation of the average. The highest average score was 17.1, while the lowest was 11.7. This is a significant difference and may suggest a difference in evaluation scores between reviewers. However, it should be noted that there was also significant variation in the quality of applications received and specific challenges – for example, challenge 3 on bottom-up projects – were associated with different qualities of application. For example,

internal reviewer R who had the lowest internal score of 11.8 was predominantly asked to review challenge 3 applications and this low score may be a reflection of the quality of applications to this challenge.

To better understand whether any individual reviewers were consistently under- or over-rating applications, we compared each applicants individual scores with the overall average for the applications they evaluated. By calculating how many standard deviations away from the mean score each rating was, we were able to build up a picture of the average level of agreement or disagreement between the reviewers. This method is somewhat imperfect, due to the standard deviation relying on a normal distribution and the small number of scores involved with just 3 for each application. Nevertheless, across the many applications, we believe this method offers a better understanding of which reviewers were most in agreement.

Reviewer	Internal/External	Average Standard Deviation
A	Internal	0.17
B	External	-0.04
C	Internal	-0.18
D	Internal	0.09
E	External	0.60
F	Internal	-0.14
G	External	0.74
H	External	-0.75
I	External	0.49
J	Internal	-0.19
K	External	0.34
L	External	-0.54
M	External	0.47
N	External	0.11
O	External	0.04
P	Internal	-0.63
Q	External	0.89

R	External	0.02
S	Internal	-0.56
T	External	0.24
U	Internal	-0.30
V	Internal	-0.30
W	Internal	-0.07
X	External	-0.17

Table 7 – Overall Average Standard Deviation from Total Average Score by Reviewer

On the whole, standard deviation scores are relatively low and no reviewer was a full standard deviation or higher from the average score (although any distance was somewhat limited by the maximum average score of 20). Nevertheless, some reviewers have high scores and 7 reviewers had scores greater than half a standard deviation (i.e., reviewers E, G, H, L, P, Q and S). One difficulty in interpreting these scores is the lack of an objective standard for evaluating projects – it is not possible to determine if any given reviewer is ‘wrong’ or evaluated too harshly or generously, merely that they evaluated more harshly or generously compared to their co-reviewers.

Any difference in scores was mitigated through a number of factors. Firstly, the use of averaging reduces the impact of any individual evaluation on a CSIs overall score. Secondly, any application with significant variation in scores or where a single reviewers’ score made the difference between being shortlisted and not being shortlisted was subsequently manually evaluated. This manual evaluation consisted of reading reviewer comments and where appropriate further discussion with reviewers. Where deemed suitable, applicants could then be invited to interview despite receiving a score below the threshold for invitation on the strength of two reviewer scores or on the basis of highly complimentary reviewer feedback. However, it should be noted that this affected only a very small number of projects and while some variation in scores was observed, this was rarely significant enough to impact the overall shortlisting decision.

To further mitigate the impact of inconsistencies in reviewer evaluations, for the third and final call we intend to moderate scores and to invite all reviewers to an event to assist in the shortlisting process. Inconsistencies between scores will be raised at this event so that reviewers can share their views and feedback and a collective decision can be made where scores and feedback differ. Guidance materials and training will be updated with further examples of projects deserving of particular scores as determined by the IMPETUS consortium. Moreover, we will leave more time for the shortlisting process and make the decision on a more holistic basis taking into account all feedback with a reduced emphasis on the scores alone.

4.5 Final Selection

The second open call received applications from 29 countries³ of which 21 were EU member states and the remaining 8 were associated countries. Figure 2 below shows the number of applications received from each country divided based on the ultimate decision made on each application. A total of 184 applications were received from EU member states, while 41 were received from associated countries.

A total of 36% of the submissions were received from applicants based in countries where the IMPETUS consortium partners are based (i.e., Austria, Italy, Spain or the UK). This is lower than the 40% received during the first call, but is still a substantial proportion. We believe that this is primarily due to these countries having large citizen science communities in a position to apply to the call. Nevertheless, we note that we once again managed to reach a range of countries outside of the more typical locations including substantial applications from Turkey and 10 countries across Southern and Eastern Europe. In combination with the first open call, we have significantly exceeded our planned KPI of applications from 20 countries.

³ Based on country of lead applicant.

Figure 2: Applications by country and evaluation status

Once again, we received a high proportion of non-male led projects: 79% of projects leads identified as female while we also received 2 applicants led by non-binary researchers. This compares favourably with the 69% of female-led applications during the first open call and exceeds our KPI of 50% non-male led projects. Further details can be seen in figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Gender of lead applicant

4.6 Evaluation Outcomes

With a total of 225 applications, we fell somewhat below the target of 450 applications we had set out in the grant agreement. This continues a trend observed in the first open call where we received 215 of 300 target applications. However, the quality of the applications continued to exceed expectations and we were not only able to select the target number of CSIs for the call, but actually recruited 3 additional CSIs in the sustaining grant category based on the strength of their applications for a total of 35 kickstarting and 13 sustaining projects. However, due to not being available during the boot (and therefore not being able to meet the contractual obligations associated with the accelerator funding), one sustaining project ultimately chose not to accept their place, leaving 12 sustaining projects.

There are a number of factors that partially explain this disparity between the target number of applications and the applications received. Firstly, informal feedback from the CSIs is that the value of the grants offered by IMPETUS are somewhat limited – €20,000 and €10,000 respectively – and this has not increased since the project began despite increases in various costs. There are competing initiatives offering additional funding and a greater time period over which to complete the project.

Another factor likely to influence the rate of applications is the somewhat restrictive nature of the IMPETUS challenges. KPIs for IMPETUS were based in part off of the application rates observed in other projects with cascading grant funding such as ACTION. However, these other projects took a much more broad approach to defining the terms of their open call. Conversely, IMPETUS sets specific thematic challenges, indicators and SDGs that projects must address. It has been possible to observe some of the impacts of these restrictions first hand: some successful kickstarting projects have indicated a willingness to seek further support through a sustaining grant, but have been unable to do so due to not aligning with the challenges of the subsequent call.

Regardless of the reasons for this disparity, we note that the quality of applications to the call has been very high and the inability to reach the target has not had a significant impact on the number of projects succeeded nor the quality and impacts of those projects.

A breakdown of the evaluation outcomes can be seen in figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Overall evaluation outcomes

The number of applications was generally well balanced between challenges with similar numbers of applications for challenges 1 (sustainable lifestyles) and 2 (justice and equity). Applications for challenge 3 were somewhat lower, but this is likely due to the restrictive nature of challenge 3 which required projects to be bottom-up, citizen-led initiatives. The number of accepted applications and total number of applications for each challenge can be seen in table 6 below. We report projects in terms of the challenge under which they were accepted and it should be noted that 4 projects which applied under challenge 3 were accepted on the basis of their suitability to other challenges⁴.

Challenge	Kickstarting Applications	Kickstarting Acceptance	Sustaining Applications	Sustaining Acceptance
Challenge 1 – Sustainable lifestyles	14	68	6	18

⁴ Three kickstarting projects were accepted under the Food, Transport, Justice and Equity (Climate) climate subchallenges respectively, while a sustaining project was accepted under the Transport subchallenge.

Challenge 2 – Justice and Equity	18	65	7	17
Challenge 3 – Citizen Science with and for Communities	3	41	0	16

Table 6: Accepted and total submissions by challenge and track

Finally, an overview of the nature of each successful applicant can be seen in table 7 below. Please note that some applicants later opted to change some of these details. We base these applicants on the data on which applications were selected only.

Type of Applicant	Count	Percentage
Consortium of Organisations	7	15
Group of Individuals	7	15
Mix of Organisations and Individuals	3	6
Single Individual	2	4
Single Organisation	29	60

Table 7: Nature of applicant type for selected applications

5 Lessons Learned

During the application process, we identified a number of key lessons that will be used to improve the third and final call. We detail these lessons below and the findings will be implemented into the documents defined for OC3, as well as the review and evaluation processes.

1. Challenge 3 (citizen science with and for communities) failed to reach the relevant communities or was seen as an opportunity to submit applications outside of the initially intended topics and subtracks. While we were able to successfully fund some projects under this challenge, the effort required on the part of the consortium was high and we have decided not to repeat this challenge for OC3.
2. Some reviewers took longer than intended to complete their reviews, which in turn resulted in delays in sending out notifications to applicants. To address this, we intend to allow for additional days for review but also a larger gap between the end of the review process and the start of the interview process. We also intend to manage more strictly manage reviewers and the review submission process. However, it should also be noted that this was in part complicated by the review period coinciding with the ECSA conference and Easter, which will not be the case for the third call.
3. Reviewers showed a tendency to assign mid-range scores (typically 3s) and to offer at times limited feedback. This resulted in a high number of similar scoring projects, but also made it difficult to identify the most important concerns to focus on at interview. Guidance materials will be revised for the third call to better distinguish between different scores and to highlight the importance of reviewer feedback. We will prioritise inviting reviewers who gave the most impactful feedback and we will provide examples of different scores to help reviewers moderate their own feedback. We also have added an extra week between reviews and invitations during which time the IMPETUS team will moderate reviews. A shortlisting event will be held during this time when we will collectively identify which applicants should be shortlisted and invited to interview.
4. Further refinement of application questions. Some applicants submitted the incorrect application form while some questions continued not to provide the required information. This was particularly the case for questions around the budget (see below), the brief description, project idea originality and key activities. We will account for this when updating the form for year 3 and ensure that it is clear to applicants that the application form has been updated. Additionally, further instructions will be added to the guide for applicants to support participants in answering these questions.
5. Many applicants failed to provide a satisfactory budget with applicants often miscalculating, under- or over-estimating overheads or omitting these altogether. This made it difficult to identify whether projects could be completed within the accelerator with the funds available. We intend to

make this clearer for the final call, but to also raise these questions at interview if budgets are not clear.

6. Eligibility criteria were one of the main sources of questions in 1:1 session discussions as well as during webinar question answering sessions. Many of the ineligible applications could have been eligible with a relatively small number of changes. We have therefore decided to run **rolling eligibility checks** where applicants receive an eligibility decision within a week of submitting, allowing them to resubmit if they choose (prior to the submission close date).
7. During the second call, 1:1 sessions were held with applicants. Applicants could sign-up for a 10 minute call with a member of the KCL IMPETUS team to ask for clarification on any questions they had. These sessions were intended to support inexperienced applicants and to offer targeted support to encourage them to apply to the accelerator. In practice, however, many applicants used these sessions to try and get feedback or guidance on their project *idea* rather than the application process. In the interests of fairness and based on the limited time available, such feedback could not be given. Since the time investment required for these sessions was relatively high and the benefits were low, we have opted not to hold these sessions for the third call, but will instead encourage new applicants to request specific email support if required.
8. While we have selected for non-male lead projects in previous calls, we noted some potentially undesirable effects and issues associated with the process of judging this criterion. These included applications that were ostensibly non-male led where the lead applicant appeared to know little about the application; the possibility that applicants could select 'prefer not to say' to circumvent being non-male led and the risk that trans or non-binary applicants may feel forced to out themselves unnecessarily. Since this was a minor judging criterion and since we have already far exceeded the anticipated number of non-male led projects, we have elected not to apply this criterion to the third call. We will explore what impact this has on the gender of applicants and will report any change in D 1.6.